

TEACHING ENGLISH STYLISTICS THROUGH LINGUACULTURAL APPROACH TO EFL STUDENTS

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Khadjieva Dilbar Tadjimuratovna

Karakalpak State University

Djumambetova Dilfuza Kongratbayevna

Karakalpak State University

Abstract

The article is about teaching English Stylistics through Linguacultural approach to EFL students. We, the authors, based on several scientists' opinions and our observations suggest our points of views on selecting texts for stylistic analysis and some activities for developing student's stylistic competencies. Also, samples of exercises designed by us based on linguacultural approach to teaching English Stylistics have been applied in the article.

INTRODUCTION

The implementation of the aspect of cultural studies in foreign language teaching is based on the formation of ideas about the language as a spiritual value, the national heritage of the people. Learning English leads to the formation of linguistic and cultural competence of students in terms of cultural studies.

In the teaching of English language, the training aimed at the formation of linguacultural competence of philologist-students is primarily based on the concept of the image of the linguistic world. The pictures of the world created and reflected by national languages differ significantly. On the one hand, it may depend on the different living conditions of people, and on the other hand, the specific characteristics of the national character. Language is closely related to the psychological structure of the ethnic group to which it belongs. When introducing students to national culture, special attention should be paid to what connects it with other national cultures and, most importantly, to what is leading and important, which has a positive effect on the formation of students' personality in modern conditions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The tasks of text stylistics include the study of the laws of the structure of opinions, concrete speech works in terms of the author's personality, the subject and always individual and non-repeating speech situations.

I.R. Galperin explains the following: "...as for the text itself, as a product of the creative process of speech, it is studied as invariants of texts in each functional style, it is subjected to linguistic analysis from the point of view of compliance or non-compliance with established laws." [1,24]

The ability to identify stylistic devices and expressive means in student's speech and to choose the ways to use them in communication, to determine whether the text belongs to a specific functional style, and to express one's communicative strategies in acceptable speech forms in English.

Working on texts of the national-cultural context in teaching foreign languages may be based on the principles introduced by N.A. Zagriadskaya and E.V. Semenyuk:

- compliance with the lexical complexity of the text, depending on the level of students' linguistic preparation, when choosing the texts for working on; [2,23]

- the ability to ensure effective interaction between the text, the environment and the reader in relation to this text; [3]

- teachers should take into account the cultural significance of the text and its ability to interest students;

- relying primarily on the interests of students when choosing texts [4,182].

When using artistic and journalistic texts with a cultural context, it is effective to take into account the criteria of relying on the genre characteristics of the texts.

Determining the topic of the work at the preliminary stage of working on the text and reading for familiarization is an important condition for a deeper understanding of the content of the text, in particular, at the level of problems and ideas.

Grammatical and lexical levels of the text, as well as its stylistic features are analyzed according to the program requirements, and then a conclusion is made about the linguistic difficulties present in the real original text. In the previous stage, the size increases during the process of working on the text, activation of passive material that needs to be activated or new linguistic material is introduced in the next stage of text processing.

Thus, when selecting texts, it is necessary to take into account many of their features.

Based on the personality-oriented approach and the approach called [5,94]"critical literacy approach" related to the opening of the author's message, the following forms of working on the text related to the topic, problem, and idea of the text are proposed.

1. Selection of quotations, aphorisms, proverbs, and conclusion formulations that correspond to the problem and ideological content of the text with further evidence in oral and written form.

2.Task according to the "vote a quote" [6,17] principle: vote for one of the quotes that best conveys the idea (problem) of the text. The task can be closed (containing the correct answer, aimed at checking understanding) or open type, that is, of a controversial nature.

3. "Just a minute" is a speaking task in which students are required to speak on one of the micro-topics of the work for 60 seconds [7,83].

The linguacultural approach to teaching English is the most traditional approach for learning literary style. [8,] Working on artistic text is the main factor in mastering stylistic devices based on this style. When the literary text is used, the history, culture, tradition, historical social-political information of the nation is obtained through the foreign language being mastered by the students. At the same time, he learns the national cultural information reflected in the text. In addition, through the translation of the artistic style that reflects the culture and values of his country, he acquires the transformation the characteristics of realia of his nation and forms the skills about it.

Selecting literary texts for teaching English stylistics is a multi-step process. Some suggest that only the works of great authors, who have not only passed the test of time, but also made a significant contribution to the study of human nature, should be considered as literature, while others recognize the relativity of any evaluations and the value of any work in relation to the trends of this historical period [9,6].

It is known that artistic texts help to form creative thinking skills and acquire knowledge aimed at perception of reality.

Tasks for the development of reading and speaking skills at the pre-text and post-text stages may be related to determining the author's position. Tasks for learning and analytical reading can be primary and secondary, universal and national-specific, based on the above distinction.

Due to the given purpose and programs of educational activities, exercises on stylistics are built in most cases in the way of working on the text. For educational purposes, texts that have undergone methodological adaptation in accordance with educational tasks at one level or another are usually used. From this point of view, an educational authentic text with both natural communication features and methodological efficiency stands out as a separate type.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A set of exercises designed by us based on a linguacultural approach to teaching "English language stylistics" ensures the practical implementation of the linguo-didactic model of the formation of unique national stylistic skills in written and oral speech in students studying English language stylistics.

For instance, such tasks may be used in EFL classroom for teaching Stylistics

Task 1: Read the given passage "Greetings in Uzbekistan" and write the words which are typical of greetings (realia) in Uzbek.

Greetings in Uzbekistan

Uzbek greetings are time consuming. Uzbeks generally greet each other with questions about family and health. Men shake hands with vigor and women sometimes hug or kiss cheeks. Men often place their left hand over their heart during a handshake to express sincerity. Most Uzbekistanis appreciate the effort a foreigner makes to learn a few Uzbek words.

Men generally do not make physical contact with women they are greeting. A woman, however, may offer a handshake. Uzbek women normally do not shake hands, and well-behaved men do not presume to greet unknown women.

A formal greeting is "Assalaam alaykum" ("Peace be unto you"). The proper response is "Vaalaykum assalaam" ("And peace also unto you"). Informally, greeters may exchange the shorter "Salaam" ("Peace").

"Yaxshimisiz?" (Are you well?) and "Qandaysiz?" (How are you?) are other common Uzbek greetings. Russians are more likely to simply shake hands and state their name.

Uzbeks address strangers as "aka" (big brother) or "opa" (big sister). "Ota" and "ona" (grandfather and grandmother) are used for the elderly. Friends and acquaintances add these terms to a person's first name. For example, a woman named Gulnora is Gulnora opa to her friends. Russians address each other by first name and a patronymic (father's first name with the suffix "ovich" or "ovna", for son or daughter). Many Uzbeks who used this form of address during the Soviet era are dropping the suffixes but retaining their father's first name as a middle name. Young people use first names only. Full names are used only in the media or in very formal situations.

Task 2: Read the passage again and define stylistic phenomenon. Try to explain what they are.

Task 3: Now work in pairs. Look at the discussion box 1 and 2 below. One of you will act as a discussion starter A, the other as a discussion starter B.

Box 1. Discussion

Discussion starter A:

You are a student who studies in a university. You are learning the English language. You meet a foreigner who is travelling in Uzbekistan and is interested in Uzbek culture. He/she ask you to inform/speak about the Uzbek greeting. How do you give information on the Uzbek people's greeting.

Box 2. Discussion

Discussion starter B:

You are a tourist who is travelling in Uzbekistan. You are interested in Uzbek culture. You meet a student who is learning English and you ask him/her to inform/speak about the Uzbek greeting. What do you ask him/her to speak about Uzbek people's greeting.

Task 4: Analyze metonymies reflecting English culture paying special attention to metonymic models containing realia in the following extracts from literary texts.

1. 'She didn't like travelling. Eastbourne was her idea of a holiday. D'you know, I'd never crossed the Channel till after her death [10,247].

2. [...] something happened which threw out many of Mr. Brewer's calculations, took away his ablest young fellows, and eventually, so prying and insidious were the fingers of the European War, smashed a plaster cast of Ceres, ploughed a hole in the geranium beds, and utterly ruined the cook's nerves at Mr. Brewer's establishment at Muswell Hill [11,105].

3. «He [Hugh Whitbread] had married this lady, the Honourable Evelyn [...]. She was one of those obscure mouse-like little women who admire big men. She was almost negligible. Then suddenly she would say something quite unexpected –

something sharp. She had the relics of grand manner, perhaps. The steam coal was a little too strong for her – it made the atmosphere thick» [11,126].

Task 5. Read the extract from the novel and answer the following questions. What English holiday is described in the extract? What lexical stylistic devices are employed by the author for creating expressiveness of description? Explain convergence of stylistic devices.

1. Everybody said: *“O, here is Maria! – when she came to Joe’s house. All the children had their Sunday dresses on. There were two big girls in from the next-door and games were going on. Maria gave the bag of cakes to the eldest boy, to divide and Mrs. Donnelly said it was too good of her to bring such a big bag of cakes, and made all the children say: «Thanks, Maria».*

Mrs. Donnelly played piano for the children and they danced and sang. Then two next door girls handed round the nuts. They arranged some Hallow Eve games and soon everything was merry. The next-door girls put some saucers on the table and then led the children up to the table, blindfold. One got the prayer book, and the other three got the water; and when one of the next-door girls got the ring Mrs. Donnelly shook her finger at the blushing girl as much as to say: O, I know all about it! They insisted on blindfolding Maria and leading her up to the table to see what she would get; and, while they were putting on the bandage, Maria laughed and laughed again till the top of her nose nearly met the tip of her chin.

*They led her up to the table amid laughing and joking, and she put her hand out in the air as she was told to do. She moved her hand about here and there in the air and descended on one of the saucers. She felt a soft wet substance with her fingers and was surprised that nobody spoke or took off her bandage. There was a pause for a few seconds; and then a great deal of scuffling and whispering. Somebody said something about the garden, and at last Mrs. Donnelly said something very cross to one of the next-door girls and told to throw it at once, that was no play. Maria understood that it was wrong that time and so she had to do it over again., and this time she got the prayer-book. After that Mrs. Donnelly played *‘Miss McCloud’s Reel’* for the children. Soon they were all quite merry again, and Mrs. Donnelly said Maria would enter a convent before the year was out because she got a prayer book [12, 118-119].*

According to R. Carter and M.N. Long: Working on literary and journalistic text, students not only improve their knowledge of the English language, but also "...improves their critical thinking" and strengthens their interpretation skills through practice [6,28]. L. Anosova recommends a cultural approach to teaching English. She prefers poetic works, including Shakespeare's sonnets, introducing

students to the history of the creation of the work and the period in which it was written [13,15].

RESULTS

The following research questions were formulated based on the selection criteria of texts in the teaching of English stylistics using literary and journalistic texts:

- What factors do teachers consider important in selecting fiction and non-fiction texts for use in English language teaching?
- How exactly do teachers use authentic literature in teaching English as a foreign language?

32 English language teachers of Karakalpak State University participated in the survey. A questionnaire was presented to the teachers - research participants in electronic form. The questionnaire was piloted with the participation of 32 teachers working in these universities.

The survey showed that, from the point of view of teachers, the most important selection criterion is the level of students' knowledge of the English language. Then, in order of importance, the lexical composition of the text is more important than the grammatical complexity. Important factors in the selection of texts are their size and socio-cultural context.

Researchers believe that the linguacultural approach to the study of literary works is effective in the process of teaching a foreign language.

Students can be offered texts that will expand their knowledge about Uzbekistan, Great Britain, The USA, Karakalpakstan, and form a positive attitude towards these country, its history, and the mentality of the English, Uzbek and Karakalpak people.

Before the first reading, it is necessary to study new vocabulary and expressive means of language describing the author's thoughts

It is necessary to pay attention to the words "having a national-cultural meaning, denoting specific objects or events related to the history, culture, economy and daily life of the people". These are: Bestobe; Kyzyl Kum; Topyrak kala, Ernazar Alakoz; Words like Nauryz, meshit, mahalle, Christmas pudding, cottage pie, pigeons, lobsters, lamb, salmon, Halloween, Forsyte, top hat, cricket, miles, etc. As noted by modern Methodologist scholars, acquaintance with such a dictionary is usually accompanied by a review of country studies.

Conclusion

In the lessons, teachers are primarily based on the level of knowledge of their students, their abilities and interests. When it comes to teaching methods, teachers prefer a linguistic approach with elements of a cultural approach

Thus, the enthusiasm of English language teachers to use linguacultural approach to learning authentic contexts may be the result of their awareness of the need to develop knowledge about different world cultures and intercultural competence that should be brought to the global modern world as a whole.

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MAILING INFORMATION

Name: Khadjieva Dilbar Tadjimuratovna

Address: Karakalpak State University, Ch.Abdirov Street 1, Nukus, Uzbekistan.

Phone number: +998913043910

Email: dilbarxadjieva2@gmail.com